

FORMATION OF AN INFORMED SOCIETY AND CRITERIA FOR ENSURING PUBLIC SAFETY

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Abstract: The article talks about the evolution of the concept of information, information society, its origins, and its essence. Also, this article analyzes the socio-philosophical and public security criteria related to the origin of the concept of information society.

Key words: information, information society, integration, globalization, internet, computer, electronics, cybernetics, social, philosophical.

INTRODUCTION

Advances in information technology and communication are changing everyone's way of life: how to work and do business, how to educate children, study and research, how to have fun - all this is changing under the influence of modern information technology. "Information society" is not only affecting human interaction, but also requires traditional organizational structures to be more flexible and decentralized.

"Information society" is a broad term used to describe the social, economic, technological and cultural changes in modern societies, especially after the Second World War, associated with the rapid development and widespread use of information and communication technologies. "Information society" is a society in which the creation, dissemination and manipulation of information has become the most important economic and cultural activity. The economic basis of the "information society" can be contrasted with predominantly industrial or agrarian societies. The tools of the "Information Society" are not lathes or plows, but computers and telecommunications.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Although the term "information society" began to be used when computerization became widespread and information and digital technologies began to actively develop, the concept of "information society" appeared in the 1940s with the emergence of cybernetics. This concept is associated with the names of American scientists K. Shannon, N. Wiener, D. von Neumann, English thinker and cryptographer A. Turing, Russian mathematician A. N. Kolmogorov. The Japanese version of the term "Information Society" appeared in a 1961 conversation between Kisho Kurokawa and Tadao Umesao. Later, this term was used in the works of T. Umesao and F. Machlup, which appeared almost simultaneously - in Japan and the USA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Information has always occupied an important place in the life of society and in the life of an individual. In the history of mankind, the process of development of the means of collecting, storing and transmitting information has not been smooth, and events of global

importance called "Information Revolution" have occurred several times in the field of information.

The first information revolution. The first information revolution is associated with the discovery of writing. Writing allowed mankind to collect knowledge and pass it down to generations. It is known that civilizations that had their own writing reached a higher economic and cultural level than others. Examples of this are Ancient Egypt, Mesopotamia, and China. In this regard, the transition from pictographic and hieroglyphic writing to alphabetic writing became particularly important.

The second information revolution. The second information revolution is associated with the invention of printing in the middle of the 16th century. This event created an opportunity not only to preserve information, but also to disseminate it to the public. Literacy left the sphere of individual classes and entered the mass. These accelerated the process of scientific and technical development. Books pushed the process of creation of universal civilization beyond the boundaries of knowledge of individual countries.

The third information revolution. The third information revolution is related to the development of communication tools at the end of the 19th century. The telegraph, telephone and radio made it possible to transmit and receive information over various distances. This stage of human development became the prelude to the process of "globalization". The development of the means of information transmission has led to the rapid development of science and technology, which requires fast and reliable means of communication.

The fourth information revolution. The fourth information revolution is associated with the emergence of microprocessor technology and, in particular, personal computers in the 70s of the 20th century. It should be noted that the information revolution was not caused by the appearance of computers in the middle of the 20th century, but by the widespread use of microprocessor systems. This process radically changed information storage and retrieval systems and led to the emergence and development of computer telecommunications. It was the fourth information revolution that became the basis for the development of the "Information Society". As a result, large flows of information were created. In the middle of the 20th century, this situation was also called the "Information explosion". According to experts, the accumulation and development of knowledge was very slow before 1900, after 1900 it doubled every 50 years, after 1950 it doubled every 10 years, from 1970 every 5 years, from the end of the 20th century is increasing by 2 times every year.

A number of political scientists and political economists emphasize that there are aspects that distinguish the concept of information society from post-industrialism. However, although the concept of the information society aims to replace the theory of post-industrial society, its proponents repeat and further develop a number of the most important tenets of technocracy and traditional futurology. D. Bell, who formed the theory of post-industrial society, is currently acting as a supporter of the concept of information society. For Bell himself, the concept of information society became a unique new stage in the development of the theory of post-industrial society. As Bell notes, "a revolution in the organization and processing of information and knowledge, in which the computer plays a central role, is developing in the context of what I call the post-industrial society."

According to James Martin, the information society means the "developed post-industrial society" that arose primarily in the West. In his opinion, it is no coincidence that the information society was first established in the countries where the post-industrial society

was formed in the 1960s and 1970s - Japan, the USA and Western Europe. James Martin tried to define and form the main characteristics of the information society according to the following criteria:

Technological criterion: Information technology, which is widely used in production, institutions, education system and daily life, is the main factor.

Social criterion: information acts as an important stimulus for changing the quality of life, forms and confirms "information consciousness" with the possibility of wide access to information.

Economic criterion: information is the main factor of the economy as a resource, service, product, source of added value and employment.

Political Criterion: Freedom of information leading to a political process characterized by growing participation and consensus among different classes and social strata of the population.

Cultural dimension: recognizing the cultural value of information by helping to establish informational values in the interests of the development of the individual and society as a whole.

At the same time, Martin emphasizes the idea that communication is "a key element of the information society."

Another British sociologist, Frank Webster, also notes five main types of information that can be used to define the information society: technological, economic, professional, spatial, and cultural. According to Webster, the nature of data has changed the way we live today. How we behave is based on theoretical knowledge and information.

Also, the large-scale implementation of information and communication and Internet technologies in all spheres of society's life has increased the urgency of the issues of protecting young people from dangers in the information field, from ideological attacks coming from abroad, and from the destructive effects of their minds. Users of social networks, computer games, and consumers of video and film products are faced with information that has a negative impact on their physical, spiritual and moral development.

In this regard, the experience of developed democratic countries is particularly noteworthy, in which these issues are solved through the following tasks:

- development of national legislation aimed at protecting young people and children in the information space;
- improving media literacy, communication etiquette in the network;
- Creation of technical mechanisms to support safe operation on the Internet;
- ensuring broad participation and mutual cooperation of state bodies, educational institutions, family, civil society institutions, mass media, etc. in solving these issues.

Formation of young people's ability to use the Internet rationally, strengthening their ideological immunity, increasing national information resources in the global network, material and moral support for young web inventors, in this regard, various contests and contests by sites conducting, encouraging young people can be an effective solution to this problem.

CONCLUSION

In fact, as long as there are threats in the information space, it is impossible to set a limit to our national information space. Therefore, creating a healthy information environment for young people and protecting the integrity of their spiritual world is one of

our main tasks. At the same time, it is necessary to include the basics of media education in the curriculum of every educational institution, to explain its basics to children in the form of interactive, various games during preschool education, to choose what is necessary for the growing generation in the intense flow of information, and to be critical of it. allows to assess with an approach. This, in turn, can be the basis for further strengthening of the citizenship position of young people in the future, for them to be able to objectively assess the events taking place in the world and make the right decisions.

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